

PHYSICOCHEMICAL PROCESSES IN THE MANUFACTURE

OF FIBER REINFORCED COMPOSITE MATERIALS

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Introduction

One of the most difficult problems in the manufacture of composite materials (CM) is the simultaneous provision of a strong bond between fiber and matrix and of a favourable interface between them. Theoretically, the formation of a strong bond between solid materials or between solid and liquid materials on each elementary area of the interface is generally assumed (1,2) to be a three-stage process (physical, contact, activation and chemical step and, finally, interaction throughout the body of the CM). The strength and the service capacity of CM will be at their highest if the third stage is limited to a relaxation of stresses which are due to strong chemical bonds being formed on the fiber-matrix interface. No mass transfer is desirable on the interaction stage, as it gives rise to new phases on the interface, this leading to a sharp drop in the strength of CM fibers and to the embrittlement of the system as a whole (3,4).

With the theory of metal reinforcement by fibers as a basis, it is possible to state that the problems which the development of new production techniques involves are essentially as follows:

- 1) Strong bonding of fiber to matrix based on chemical bonds on the interface between them.
- 2) Least diffusion and formation of no new phases between

the fiber and the matrix.

3) Maximum retention of fiber strength.

4) Uniform distribution of a specified amount of fibers throughout the body of the matrix.

5) Possibility of using efficient techniques to form finished items of complicated shapes without damage to fibers.

Let us examine now to what extent the current CM production techniques meet the above requirements (see Table I).

Table I. Main Parameters of Various Techniques for CM Production

CM manufacturing technique	State of aggregation of material		Duration of process	Temperature of process	Pressure kgf/mm ²
	matrix	fiber			
1. Hot pressing, thermal compressing welding	solid	solid	sec.-min.	(0.6-0.8) T_m of matrix	0.2-6
2. Hot rolling	solid	solid	sec.	(0.6-0.8) T_m of matrix	0.2-6
3. Explosion welding	solid	solid	10^{-5} - 10^{-6} s.	(0.3-1.0) T_m of matrix	200-700
4. Infiltration	liquid	solid	sec.-min.	Above T_m of matrix	-
5. Moulding	liquid	solid	sec.-min.	Above T_m of matrix	-
6. Drawing of fibers through molten matrix	liquid	solid	10^{-1} sec	- " -	-
7. Plasma deposition	solid	solid	10^{-2} - 10^{-4} sec.	0.8 T_m of matrix	1-5

The first two methods are based on solid-phase bonding of matrix to fiber parallel with compaction of CM. The temperature and the duration of these processes are sufficiently great, so that there are no means to confine the fiber-matrix interaction to the interface and thus to obtain a high-quality CM.

In explosion pressing (explosion welding), the interaction

is brief, but a high-pulse pressure of the explosion tends to damage (break up) the fibers. The technique is thus suitable to metal wire reinforcing only.

The first two techniques are best suited to the manufacture of refractory CM reinforced by fibers with barrier anti-diffusion coats. In addition, both these methods provide good results as regards the bonding and the compaction of matrices in semi-products manufactured by plasma deposition.

The manufacture of CM based on liquid-phase techniques (points 4 through 6) requires adequate wetting of fibres by the molten matrix. Fibers are, in some instances, given a special coat to improve their wettability (5). The least duration of interaction is that in high-velocity drawing of fibers through the molten matrix metal. The duration of phase interaction may then be limited to 10^{-1} s, this being sufficient to avoid the formation of undesirable structures on the fiber-matrix interface for a number of pairs of materials (6).

The first four problems in CM manufacture are readily solved by a plasma deposition of the matrix metal upon the reinforcing fibers. Due to a high temperature and a high velocity, the projected particles bond strongly to the fibers. The particles deposited on the fibers solidify and cool rapidly, and, therefore, the duration of the interaction is small, and no secondary phases are formed in the fiber-matrix boundary region. However, the plasma-deposited matrix is porous, its relative density ranging from 85 to 95%. A reduced density is inherent in all the deposited materials generally. In this case, the porosity of the matrix is additionally increased by the shadow effect due to fibers. A deposited matrix may be further compacted and strengthened, and finished items may be formed from plasma-deposited semi-fabricates by hot pressing, rolling, infiltration with metallic melts and other means. Plasma techniques provide great potentialities for the manufacture of CM intended for service at relatively low temperatures when no fiber-matrix interaction (heterogeneous and reaction diffusion) takes place. The plasma techniques then often eliminate the need for barrier coats on fibers.

Theoretical Considerations

Let us discuss the physicochemical principles underlying plasma techniques for the manufacture of CM.

As the strength of fibers is much greater than that of the matrix the lattice bond energies in various materials will also differ substantially (Table II).

Table II. Energy Characterizing Chemical Bond in Lattice of Some Materials: Heat of Sublimation for Metals and Average Energy of Unit Bonds Me-O for Oxides (the bracketed values are energies of dissociation to atoms of oxides)

<u>Reinforcing fibers</u>		<u>Metallic matrices</u>	
<u>Material</u>	<u>Energy kcal/mole</u>	<u>Metal</u>	<u>Energy kcal/mole</u>
Al ₂ O ₃	61 (370)	Al	75
B	130	Mg	35
W	200	Ag	67
Mo	157	Cu	80
SiO ₂	104 (410)	Ni	101
		Ti	112

The formation of strong bonds, based on chemical bonding, between fibers and matrix will be limited by the fiber surface activation step, since the bond energy in fibers is higher than that in matrices. The fiber activation step will require a greater amount of energy than compaction and strengthening of a more plastic matrix.

In plasma deposition, the energy of activation of matrix-particle and fiber bonding is governed by that of the fiber surface (7). For metallic reinforcing fibers, the relevant activation energy E_a will be close to half of the bond energy E_s in the fiber metal lattice ($E_a \leq E_s/2$). The activation energy may be minimized still further by increasing the pressure in the particle-fiber contact region through a greater particle deposition velocity. A maximum drop in the activation energy takes place through a shear occurring at the expense of the friction contact forces between the particle and the support when the

deformation due to the applied external pressure is strongly localized in the contact (1,8,9). However, the velocity (and, therefore, the pressure) of the particles is to be carefully controlled where non-metallic fibers are involved, so as not to reduce their strength or damage them.

A substantial advantage of plasma deposition of matrix is the short-duration of action of particles upon fibers. Calculations tend to indicate that the duration of an active interaction between fibers and the metal of the matrix is 10^{-2} to 10^{-4} s, this value representing the duration of both the thermal and the mechanical actions of the particles upon the fibres. The intensities of the thermal and the dynamic actions of the particles are sufficient to initiate and complete processes resulting in a strong chemical bonding. The short duration of the action restricts recrystallization, diffusion mass transfer and nucleation of new phases. It is thus possible, for example, to deposit and bond strongly nickel to steel fibers with no adverse effect upon latter's strength.

The chemical process between the deposited matrix and the fibers and their strong bonding is describable, for isothermic conditions, by an activation equation of the type below (7):

$$t = -\frac{1}{\nu} \ln \left[1 - \frac{N(t)}{N_0} \exp\left(\frac{E_a}{kT}\right) \right] \quad (1)$$

where: t - duration of interaction;

ν - frequency of intrinsic vibrations of atoms;

T - temperature of the process;

N_0 - number of atoms on the fiber surface in contact with matrix particle;

$N(t)$ - number of atoms in contact that have reacted during the time t ;

K - Boltzmann constant.

This equation has been derived with the aid of one of the simplest approximations of the physicochemical theory of interaction of materials in the course of deposition, said approximation neglecting the pressure due to impacts of particles. Practice has justified the use of this equation, as it permits quantitative evaluations of the interaction of materials at particle

deposition velocities of 50 to 100 m/s, the ratio $N(t)/N_0$ is determined roughly on the basis of the experimentally obtained relative shear strength $\tau \left(\frac{N(t)}{N_0} \approx \frac{\tau(t)}{\tau_{max}} \right)$ of the bond formed during the time t of the fiber-matrix interaction.

Plasma deposition is used to apply matrix metal upon reinforcing fibers wound on drums or laid to a very high pitch accuracy. The resultant single-layer CM semi-fabricate is cut to blanks, placed in a stack and subjected to hot pressing, the deposited matrix being compacted, and the layers of semi-fabricates, strongly bonded together in the process. Hot pressing is effected at more moderate temperatures and over a considerably greater period of time than the plasma deposition. The diagram illustrating the variations of the pressure P and the temperature T with the time and the possible ranges of these production processes are presented in Fig. I.

The strength of the bond between the fiber and the matrix deposited by a plasma technique may be experimentally determined by a method consisting in "pulling" a fiber out of a model

Fig. I - The diagram illustrating the variations of the temperature $T(t)$ and pressure $P(t)$ which provide a strong bonding between the fiber and the matrix in plasma deposition (a), and process conditions for compaction of matrix in hot pressing (b); T_m - melting point of material of matrix.

which simulates the CM matrix (10). The matrix is applied in a uniform layer upon the side surface of a fiber, the layer thickness being equal to 3 or 4 fiber diameters. The end face of the fiber is not coated. The fiber is then loaded in a manner to pull it out of the matrix. For a certain critical length l_c of the coated section of the fiber, the latter can no longer be pulled out of the matrix and so ruptures. The shear stress is calculated from the equation of the equilibrium of an element of a fiber and a matrix (10)

$$\tau = \frac{\sigma_f \cdot d_f}{2l_c} \quad (2)$$

where: σ_f - tensile strength of fiber;
 d_f - fiber diameter.

The bonding strength between a deposited aluminium matrix and a steel fiber (Fig.2) varies inversely with the fiber dia-

Fig. 2 - Variation in the bonding strength between an aluminium matrix and a grade EP 322 steel as a function of the fiber heating temperature T_f : 1 and 2 are experimental curves for fiber diameters $d_f=150$ and 300 mk; 3 is the curve calculated according to the equation (3) for $\nu = 10^{13} \text{ s}^{-1}$, $t=10^{-3} \text{ s}$; $E_a=1.8 \text{ eV}$. T was calculated as a function of T_f according to the equation (4) of the work (7).

meter: the curve 1 for the fiber diameter $d_f = 150$ mk passes above the curve 2 for fiber diameter $d_f = 300$ mk. A heating of the fiber to a temperature T_f sharply increases the strength of its bonding to the matrix. The maximum bonding strength attained in this CM was $\tau = 7-8$ kgf/mm². A decrease in fiber diameter lowers the critical length l_c and permits a same strength τ to be attained at a lesser fiber heating temperature as compared to a fiber of a greater diameter. This is due to that a reduction in fiber diameter increases both the intensity of the thermal action of particles upon fibers and the extent of chemical interaction at the interface.

The kinetics of the chemical reaction between the matrix and the fiber and the increase in the strength may be described by the equation (I), which is presented in the form below

$$\frac{N(t)}{N_0} = I - \exp \left[- \frac{U t}{\exp \left(\frac{E_0}{kT} \right)} \right] \quad (3)$$

On Fig.2 the calculated curve 3 satisfactorily describes the qualitative aspect of the variation of the bond between the matrix and the fiber with the fiber heating temperature.

A successful developemnt and application of a fiber reinforced CM hinges today mainly on a theoretically supported choice of a technique for manufacturing the CM. The theoretical approaches to the solution of these problems are sufficiently clear. However, it is necessary to provide, for each specific fiber-matrix pair, an appropriate combination of concrete process techniques and conditions to ensure optimum properties of resultant CM.

Production Process

The plasma serves as a source of energy for heating, melting, atomizing and depositing a matrix in the form of particles of 20 to 200 mk across upon the reinforcing fiber. The deposited particles are accelerated by the plasma to a velocity of 100 to 150 m/s, intensively deformed upon impact and thus caused to penetrate between the fibers to provide a fine-grained

matrix.

The greatest problem in the development of production techniques and process parameters for manufacturing CM is related to a requirement of providing a high bonding strength between the fiber and the matrix σ_{f-m} while retaining the strength of the fiber proper σ_f . This requirement can be met only by an accurate conformance to process parameters, as, on the one hand, the deposition conditions are required to ensure an adequate physicochemical interaction and a strong bonding of the fiber to the matrix at the interface and, on the other hand, have no substantial effect upon the properties of fibers. One of the most convenient process means for controlling the interaction of the materials is the thermal activation of the process, this being achieved by an appropriate increase in the temperature T_f of the fiber during the deposition of the matrix. However, there is a limit in the temperature rise above which the strength of the fibers falls off.

Let us consider now the diagram which shows the variation of the fiber-matrix bonding strength σ_{f-m} and of the fiber strength σ_f as a function of the fiber temperature T_f (Fig.3). The fiber-matrix bonding strength is represented by the curve A, while the curves I through III describe the possible variants of fiber strength σ_f . The effect of the thermal activation upon the bonding strength is observable at temperatures not exceeding, generally, the 150 to 200°C range.

Some reinforcing materials, such as silicon carbide fibers and tungsten wire, retain their strength even at relatively high temperatures. By contrast, the heating of a boron fiber above 500°C lowers its strength. The heating range over which fiber strength drops rapidly is approximately 200°C. Therefore, there will be three possible variants (I through III) of properties of the fiber and of its bonding strength to matrices A and B, depending on the type of fiber and the thermal conditions necessary to provide a strong bond to the matrix.

I. The temperature T required to form a strong bond σ_{f-m} between the fiber and the matrix A has no effect upon the initial fiber strength σ_f (I). This interaction variant makes it possible to obtain CM semi-fabricates from a given pair of materials in a wide range of process conditions according to a

Fig. 3 - Diagram illustrating the possible variants of the intersect of curves, expressing the relationship between the fiber-matrix bonding strength σ_{f-m} and the fiber temperature T_f , with the curves representing the variations in the strength of fibers σ_f under the action of plasma, deposited particles and fiber heating temperature.

most simple technique.

2. The temperature T_I which provides a satisfactory bonding strength between the fiber and the matrix lowers the fiber strength σ_f (II). If the strength drop is within admissible limits, there is a narrow range ΔT of thermal conditions for obtaining the semi-fabricate, and the production process should be based on this range. This type of interaction is widely met with in practice, and in particular, is the one taking place in the manufacture of aluminium-boron CM.

3. Low bonding strength σ_{f-m} corresponding to a sharp drop in fiber strength σ_f (III). This type of interaction takes place, e.g., in deposition of nickel or titanium upon boron or silicon carbide fibers.

The properties of the resultant semi-fabricate may correspond to one of the above variants, depending on the materials used as the matrix and the fiber. The first two variants are

capable of providing satisfactory properties of the semi-fabricate, whereas the third variant necessarily involves the development and the use of special techniques for plasma deposition of the matrix upon the fibers to retain the latter's properties. This variant is usually met with when the reinforcement is provided by non-metallic fibers.

There are two ways to improve the properties of semi-fabricates obtained by plasma deposition:

1. To lower the temperature of formation of a strong bond between the fiber and the matrix, i.e., to shift the σ_{f-m} curve from position A to position B, and, correspondingly, to manufacture the semi-fabricate at a lower temperature T_2 .

2. To use special techniques, so as to retain, at given process temperatures, the initial or sufficiently high properties of the fibers, i.e., to effect the deposition in a manner to make the variation of fiber properties conform to curve I or II.

A strong bonding of the matrix to the fiber at a lesser overall heating of the latter in a real deposition process is obtainable by heating the particles above the melting point, increasing the pressure of the particles on impact (i.e., increasing their velocity) or providing a longer time of interaction t . In some instances, good results may be obtained by using reinforcing fibers of a lesser diameter (see Fig.2). An alternative way to enhance the properties of semi-fabricates may include the following procedures and operations: application of special coats upon fibers; conducting plasma deposition in a controlled atmosphere; development and use of new special means and methods for plasma deposition of the matrix upon the fibers.

A plasma technology may be suggested for manufacturing CM consisting of aluminium, nickel and their alloys reinforced by SiC-coated boron fibers, SiC fibers and carbon fibers. Experiments have shown that a plasma deposition at optimum conditions lowers the strength of fibers by not more than 5 to 15% as compared to the initial strength (Fig.4, a and b). The optimum thickness of the SiC protective coat is 2 to 4 mk (Fig.5). A thinner coat is inadequate for the protection of fibers against

Fig. 4 - Variation of the relative strength $\sigma(L)/\sigma_0$ of boron and silicon carbide fibers on deposition by aluminium (a) and nickel (b) as a function of the deposition distance L : 1 - boron fiber with no coat; 2 - boron with a B_4C coat 2 to 3 mk thick; 3 - boron fiber with a SiC coat 2 to 3 mk thick; 4 - SiC fiber with no coat.

the action of particles, whereas a thicker coat impairs fiber strength. A metallographic analysis of the surface of a thick coat after the matrix particles have been deposited has revealed the formation of cracks in the coat which penetrates deep into the fiber.

It is a known fact that the strength of reinforced materials is governed by the volumetric fraction v_f of the fiber in the CM. The properties of CM obtained from plasma semi-fabricates agree well with the theoretical strength of composites σ_c as expressed by a simple additive law

$$\sigma_c = \sigma_f \cdot v_f + \sigma_m^+ (1 - v_f)$$

where: σ_m^+ - matrix strength;
 σ_f - fiber strength.

Fig. 5 - Relationship between the relative strength of boron fibers coated by silicon carbide and the thickness of coat on deposition of nickel: 1 - $L = 50$ mm; 2 - $L = 100$ mm; 3 - $L = 150$ mm.

The properties of CM are governed in many respects by the initial strength of the reinforcing fibers. Even with a low-grade boron fibre and an aluminium matrix the plasma CM features the following properties: strength, $\sigma = 130$ kgf/mm²; modulus, $E = 20,000$ kgf/mm²; specific strength, 45 km; specific modulus, 8,000 km; density, 2.6 g/cm³. The microstructure of the CM fracture (Fig.6) shows that the fiber and the matrix in this CM fail simultaneously. A similar fracture characterizes a strong bonding of the boron fiber in the matrix based on the formation of chemical bonds along the interface.

Fig. 6 - Character of fracture of an aluminium-boron composite material.

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